

ACHIEVEMENTS OF WOMEN AND GIRLS IN SPORTS IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article is written about the role of women in physical education. Based on any social structure, along with the reproductive capabilities of women, their role in the formation and development of the new generation is incomparable. There are basic principles to guarantee equal rights and opportunities for women and men in society, which are legality, democracy, equal rights of women and men, non-discrimination on the basis of gender, openness and transparency.

A woman and her role in the life of society has always been an important criterion, The development of any state and society is based on a number of factors. In this process, the issue of women, their participation in social and political relations, the fact that their rights and freedoms are ensured is an important index of the development of states and democracy. After all, a woman and her role in the life of society have always been an important criterion. Based on any social structure, along with the reproductive capabilities of women, their role in the formation and development of the new generation is incomparable. There are basic principles to guarantee equal rights and opportunities for women and men in society, which are legality, democracy, equal rights of women and men, non-discrimination on the basis of gender, openness and transparency.

The role of women, their political and legal culture is of particular importance in the chain of development of Uzbekistan as a state and society, which has a worthy place among the countries of the world and in the international community.

In today's globalization process, the place and role of women is more important than ever in the matter of forming an active citizenship position of the new generation in relation to any conditions. Therefore, the main content of the reforms is to support women to come up with new ideas and initiatives, to ensure their active participation in the efforts, changes and social-political processes implemented in our country. After all, if we say that glorifying the value of a person is first of all realized by respecting women, honoring our respectable mothers, and appreciating our virtuous sisters, we will be telling the same truth. We can say with recognition that today our women and girls are actively leading in the field of sports as well as in other fields.

It should be noted that today, under the leadership of our President, new laws and decisions are being adopted in the field of sports. Taekwondo was not left out. zbegim's beautiful girls, there are many of our girls who are going to the world arenas and raising the flag of Uzbekistan. Including Svetlana Osipova, to introduce the flag of Uzbekistan to the whole world. Over the past years, the number of girls engaged in taekwondo was small, but now, if you look at the general sports, the number of girls is much larger. Based on this, our sports are developing much more widely.

Svetlana Osipova A number of major international taekwondo WT tournaments were held in the capital of Iran. Our national team successfully participates in these starts and defends the honor of our city. For example, according to the results of 3 prestigious competitions, our famous athlete, participant of Tokyo-2020 Svetlana Osipova filled the coffers of our delegation with 3 medals. First, Osipova entered the top three at the Asian Club Championship held in Tehran on March 4-5. Then, on March 6-9, he climbed to the top of the podium at the traditional "Fajr" open tournament. Also, our hero defeated all his opponents in the "Asian Taekwondo Federation President's Cup" competition and became the champion once again.

It is the same sport, but our para-taekwondo female athletes are fighting for Uzbekistan with honor as if they were defending their country. We are proud to say this.

Our para taekwondo champions.

At the Asian Para-Taekwondo Championship held in Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam, the national team of Uzbekistan won 2 gold, 1 silver and 3 bronze medals and took second place

after Iran in the team score. Guljanoy Naimova, who competed in the 65 kg weight category, won a gold medal. Ziyoda Isokova won the silver medal for the national team in the women's competition in the -47 kg weight category. In addition, more than 100 athletes from 21 countries participated in the competition, and the Uzbekistan national team was recognized as the best team of the Asian Championship. The coach of the national team, Bobur Koziyev, was recognized as the best coach of the competition.

The main goal of Taekwondo is humanity, justice, wisdom, spirituality and trust, to prevent the strong from oppressing the weak, and to build a good society. Taekwondo should never be used for selfish or aggressive purposes, as an individual or group, as a means of commercial or political pressure. Taekwondo also teaches the importance of being responsible and honest, and the importance of being in harmony with society. A true Taekwondo athlete knows how to behave when and where.

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